

PSYCHOLINGUISTIC CHARACTERISTICS IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO YOUNG LEARNERS

Shokhsanam Rashid kizi Ibragimova

Humo Academy School, English teacher

The purpose of the study is investigating the effectiveness of various psycholinguistic characteristics and teaching strategies for young English language learners. It aims to explore how these factors can enhance language acquisition and create a stimulating learning environment. The study was conducted at the Educational Language Center in Tashkent, Uzbekistan, with a focus on the application of songs, pictorial illustration, and Total Physical Response (TPR) strategies.

Theoretical Framework:

Psycholinguistics, the study of the psychological processes involved in language, provides valuable insights into effective language teaching. Key psycholinguistic factors considered in this research include:

- **Language Acquisition:** Understanding the natural process of language acquisition helps tailor teaching methods to align with learners' cognitive development.
- **Cognitive Development:** Young learners' cognitive abilities, such as memory, attention, and problem-solving skills, influence their learning styles and preferences.
- **Affective Factors:** Creating a positive and supportive learning environment is crucial for fostering motivation, self-esteem, and overall language learning success.

Methodology:

The study involved a quasi-experimental design, with two groups of young learners (aged 7-10) participating in different teaching strategies. One group focused on songs, while the other used pictorial illustration, both integrated with TPR. Pre- and post-tests were administered to assess language proficiency before and after the intervention.

Findings:

The results of the study revealed significant improvements in both groups, highlighting the effectiveness of the selected strategies. Key findings include:

- Songs and TPR: The combination of songs and TPR proved to be highly effective in enhancing listening, pronunciation, and vocabulary acquisition.
- Pictorial Illustration and TPR: Visual aids, combined with TPR, supported visual learners and facilitated understanding of new concepts.
- Language Background: The learners' prior language experiences and exposure to English influenced their learning outcomes.

Discussion and Implications:

The findings of this study have several implications for teaching English to young learners:

- Integration of Psycholinguistic Principles: Incorporating psycholinguistic principles into teaching practices can create more effective and engaging learning experiences.
- Variety of Strategies: Employing a variety of teaching strategies, including songs, visuals, and TPR, can cater to different learning styles and enhance language acquisition.
- Positive Learning Environment: Creating a supportive and enjoyable learning environment is essential for young learners' motivation and overall language development.

Conclusion:

This thesis demonstrates the effectiveness of using psycholinguistic principles and a variety of teaching strategies to enhance English language learning in young learners. The findings highlight the importance of tailoring instruction to learners' cognitive development, affective needs, and language background. By incorporating these factors, teachers can create engaging and effective language learning experiences that foster long-term language proficiency.

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